
**LANGUAGE AND COMMUNICATION: A RHETORICO ANALYSIS
OF PRESIDENT MUHAMMADU BUHARI'S SPEECH OF AUGUST
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Abstract

This paper seeks to analyze President Buhari's August 11, 2022 speech on the March 28, 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack by bandits in compliance with rhetorical canons and proofs. The data for the study comprised President Muhammadu Buhari's speech on the March 28, 2022 train attack delivered on the 11th August, 2022. The content analysis procedure was adopted to assess the speech published by Vanguard and The Guardian newspapers of August 12, 2022. The video was downloaded to aid the analysis by comparing both the video and the transcript to ensure its unity. Analyses were carried out to determine if the speech conformed to rhetorical canons, and the extent to which the speech adhered to rhetorical proofs. To give this study a backing, the Critical Discourse Analysis and the Systemic Functional Linguistics (SFL) theories were adopted. Findings reveal that President Muhammadu Buhari's speech on the March 28, 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack failed to conform to rhetorical canons and proofs. In view of this, it was recommended that Presidential speech writers should consider the importance of adopting the three rhetorical proofs – logos, ethos and pathos as well as the five rhetorical canons of invention, arrangement, style, memory and delivery in future speech writing in order to inspire, arouse and appeal to emotions. The study also recommends that efforts should be intensified to improve the President's ability to use the rhetorical canon of memory in future speeches as such efforts would help to reduce his over dependence on the script.

Keywords: Critique, Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack, Rhetoric Canons, Rhetoric Proofs, Communication

Background of The Study

Ideally, presidential speeches the world over are meant to inspire, uplift, motivate, unite, show empathy, be sensitive to the mood of the moment and presidential in nature. Speech delivery is important; whoever is giving a speech should oversee not just its creation, but also its execution. This is because the speaker's method of delivery can have just as much effect on the audience's reception as the content of the speech itself. The writing and execution of political speeches require numerous elements of political communication. Although there is much debate about which parts of this process are the most essential, there is no doubt that its organization should place as much emphasis as possible on every detail, including composition and delivery.

Noermanzah (2018) states that rhetoric is the practice in the use of the language of influencing others to achieve planned goals, characterized by certain credibility (ethos), the ability to manage listeners' emotions (pathos), and the use of logic (logos). Similarly, Larson (2017) states that rhetoric is the intelligent ability to use the means of language in the process of persuasion, which can be done using ethics (ethos), emotional appeal (pathos), or reason (logos).

On 28 March 2022, at about 7:45 pm, a train traveling from Abuja to Kaduna was attacked in Katari, Kaduna State by bandits after bombing the rail track, killing at least eight passengers while 168 others were kidnapped or declared missing. An eyewitness report has it that 970 passengers were on board the train, and that many of them may have been abducted into the bush by the marauding bandits, who carried out the attack on motorcycles, holding firearms and other deadly weapons.

The train is said to have departed the Idu train station in Abuja at 6 pm and was scheduled to arrive at Rigasa train station in Kaduna at 8 pm. Reports have it that the assailants bombed the train twice before they opened fire on the passengers. According to the reports, although 26 passengers were officially declared missing, the whereabouts of over 150 of them could not be ascertained almost two weeks after the incident (Wikipedia, 2022). Many relatives of the kidnapped victims besieged the headquarters of the Ministry of Transportation in Abuja and demanded the immediate release of the captives.

However, before now, the bandits had released a video clip showing the male

hostages being flogged as they cried and called on the Federal Government to come to their rescue. The group recently released 11 of the hostages, a deal facilitated by a controversial Kaduna-based Islamic cleric, Ahmad Gumi. Also, during the Ramadan celebrations, the bandits released the Managing Director of the Bank of Agriculture, Alwan Hassan, after a ransom payment.

On Sunday, the terrorists released a viral video where they were seen flogging their hostages. They also threatened to abduct President Muhammadu Buhari and the Kaduna State Governor, Nasir El-Rufai. In what could be described as panic response, the Presidency reacted to the threat a few hours after, accusing the insurgents of using propaganda to compel the government to yield to their demands.

The Senior Special Assistant to President Muhammadu Buhari on Media and Publicity, Garba Shehu, in a statement made available to newsmen, said security forces are not helpless in stemming the tide of insecurity confronting the country and that as Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces, President Muhammadu Buhari has been supporting security agencies by boosting their morale and providing the needed equipment. According to him;

The Presidency, in the meantime wishes to reassure the public that the President has done all, and even more than what is expected of him as Commander-in-Chief by way of morale, material and equipment support to the military and expects nothing short of good results in the immediate aftermath of the incident.

When the relatives of the kidnapped victims met with the President, instead of restoring their confidence and patriotism in the leadership of the nation by deploying the rhetorical canons to show sensitivity to their plight, he worsened the situation and even demoralized them the more by categorically telling them that his decision to stop maximum use of military force against terrorists to rescue the remaining victims of the Kaduna train attack was to avoid collateral damage. He told representatives of the families that in the immediate aftermath of the incident, several actions had been taken by government to bring succour to the affected families and prevent a recurrence in the country. In the rhetorical sense, this claim lacked ethos, pathos and logos. To the President, “the condition to guarantee a successful outcome and minimize potential collateral

damage could not be assured and, therefore, that course of action had to be reluctantly discarded. My primary concern is to get everyone released safe and unhurt.” The question left on the minds of his listeners was, how?

On his instruction to security and law enforcement agencies to bring an end to inhumane action against innocent Nigerians, the President said;

Judging by the available reports to me and news that have begun emerging in the last few days, I wish to say they (the security and law enforcement agencies) have heard this instruction and are responding appropriately. In the past couple of days, you must have heard about the number of terrorists neutralised by the military, and the number of hostages freed. These efforts will not stop or reduce.

The response from one of the representatives of the families of the victims, Mr. Sabiu Mohammed, while appealing to the Federal Government to assist them in the release of their remaining loved ones indicates that they were not convinced that the President has done all he should. He said, “please we want to see our loved ones and many have found themselves in very critical situations. We do not have the money they (the kidnapers) are demanding. Please, Mr. President, we know you are doing your best... please, please we want to see our loved ones.”

Statement of The Problem

Speeches by presidents are powerful as they not only carry the weight of policy statement or direction but possess the ability to inspire, uplift, motivate, unite, show empathy, be sensitive to the mood of the moment, as well as incite, arouse, mobilize, rally and galvanize a people towards an intended outcome. Whoever is giving the speech should oversee not just its creation but also its execution, because the speaker's method of delivery can have just as much effect on the audience's reception as the rhetoric it contains. This paper takes a critique at President Muhammadu Buhari's August 11, 2022 speech to families of the March 28, 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack victims and juxtaposes it with the five rhetorical canons - invention, arrangement, style, memory and delivery as well as the rhetorical proofs - Ethos, Pathos and Logos as theorized by Aristotle. Hence, to what extent did President Buhari's speech on March 28, 2022 train-attack conform to rhetorical canons and proofs?

Objectives of The Study

The objectives of this study were to:

1. Find out if President Buhari's speech on the March 28, 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack conformed to the Rhetorical Canons;
2. Determine the extent to which rhetorical proofs were complied with in president Buhari's speech on March 28, 2022 train attack.

Review of Literature

Rhetoric

Rhetoric is a Greek word meaning “speaker” and is used for the art of persuasive speaking or writing. It is speaking or writing that is intended to please or persuade. Rhetoric is also the study of the technique and rules for using language effectively, especially in public speaking. It entails the high-style of excessive use of verbal ornamentation.

Canons of Rhetoric

According to a Roman Philosopher, Cicero, there are five canons or tenets of rhetoric. They are: invention, arrangement, style, memory, and delivery. Although these canons were originally created with a focus on oratory or public speaking, today, most are also applicable to the writing process stages of prewriting, drafting and rewriting.

Invention

Invention is the process of coming up with material for a text. It is the stage of brainstorming. Before writing a paper, a writer does a free writing exercise to come up with a good topic. For example, when a politician creating the several major points he hopes to include in a speech.

Arrangement

Arrangement is the process of deciding how to order the materials in text. In writing, this is also part of the prewriting stage. A writer creates an outline to determine the order in which he will discuss his major points.

Style

Style is the process of coming up with the actual words that will be used in a text. In writing, this canon is first approached in the drafting stage and then continued in the rewriting stage. For example, when a politician uses

humorous metaphor in which he compares being among human beings to being in the zoo. Style also involves the consideration sentence structures, changing passive to active voice and vice versa depending on the situation.

Memory

Memory has to do with the process of committing a text to memory. Although this canon is not as applicable to writing as it is to oratory, there are still occasions where writers must memorize their texts in order to make the delivery more effective. This involves rehearsing and practicing the speech so that one does not need to use a teleprompter or script. When this is done, one is able to make eye contact with the audience and effectively use the body language.

Delivery

Delivery is the process of presenting a text to an audience. Like memory, delivery is less prominent in writing than in oratory; however, there are many occasions when writers must think of how best to deliver their texts. For example, as a politician delivers his speech, he shows energy by speaking in a loud voice and pounding the podium with his fist. At an academic conference, the speaker walks round the room as he delivers his paper instead of standing behind the podium the whole time.

Rhetorical proofs

The rhetorical proofs – logos, ethos and pathos are important components of all writing, whether we are aware of them or not. By learning to recognize logos, ethos and pathos in the speeches or writing of others and in our own, we can create text that appeal to the audience in many different levels.

Logos - Logos appeals to reason. Logos can also be thought of as the text of the argument, as well as how well a speaker has argued his or her point.

Ethos - Ethos appeals to the speaker or writer's character. Ethos can also be thought of as the role of the speaker or writer in the argument, and how credible his or her argument is.

Pathos - Pathos appeals to the emotions and the sympathetic imagination, as well as to beliefs and values. Pathos can also be thought of as the role of the audience in the argument. Aristotle taught that a speaker's ability to persuade an audience is based on how well the speaker appeals to that audience in three

different areas: logos, ethos and pathos. He added that when considered together, these appeals form what later rhetoricians termed the 'rhetorical triangle' (Insert rhetorical triangle).

Questions to Help Recognize and Utilize Rhetorical Proofs

The following questions can be used in two ways both to think about how we use logos, ethos and pathos in speech and or writing, and also to assess how other speakers and writers use them in their speeches and writings.

Logos

- Is the thesis clear and specific?
- Is the thesis supported by strong reasons and credible evidence?
- Is the argument logical and arranged in a well-reasoned order?

Ethos

- What are the speaker/writer's qualifications? How has the speaker/writer connected himself to the topic being discussed?
- Does the speaker/writer demonstrate respect for multiple viewpoints by using sources in the text?
- Are the sources credible? Are sources documented appropriately?
- Does the speaker use a tone that is suitable for the audience/purpose? Is the diction (word choice) used appropriately for the audience/purpose?
- Is the document presented in a polished and professional manner?

Pathos

- Are vivid examples and details used to engage the reader's emotions and imagination?
- Does the speaker/writer appeal to the values and beliefs of the reader by using examples readers relate to or care about?

President Muhammadu Buhari's Speech Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims on August 11, 2022 and Its Conformity to the Rhetoric Canons of Communication: An overview

According to Esuh (2006), all rhetoric is divided into five parts of *inventio*, *dispositio*, *elucutio*, *memoria* and delivery. Each of these parts has its distinctive functions in rhetorical communication. They form part of oratorical order as well as forms for critical analysis and evaluation. This assertion is based on Aristotle's classical traditions known as *ad herennium*. Pudewa

(2016) also states that to most modern minds, the phrase, 'rhetoric smacks of cunning', suggests empty polemic or self-aggrandizement of a political figure, or perhaps the crafty prose of a present-day sophist who is trying to sell an overpriced or unnecessary products to the unlearned.

It is worthy of note here that in classical education, rhetoric is the third liberal art, the top of the trivium, the noble art of persuasion, a skill in the tradition of Plato and Paul, Cicero and Augustine, which since ancient times, has been practiced and applied for noble (and sometimes) ignoble purposes.

Walton (2000) states that the five canons of rhetoric are a classical approach to understanding effective communication. These canons of rhetoric are invention (what to say), arrangement (structure of content), style (language choices), memory (learn the presentation) and delivery (use of more than just words). These elements of rhetoric are simply the five skills that individuals need to have to be great at communicating.

According to Pudewa (2016), the word *canon* is most commonly used in music to describe a piece in which a melody is introduced in different parts successively. It is also used in expressions like 'the canon of literature' which denotes a collection of books comprising a set such as the *Scripture or the Great Books*. A simpler definition of the word *canon* is a general rule, law, or principle. The Five Canons of Rhetoric give us five general principles or divisions which, when understood and applied, will make our communication more effective. These principles are commonly labeled as invention, arrangement, elocution, memory, and delivery (Pudewa, 2016).

Interestingly, Brett and McKay (2020) state that the five canons of rhetoric constitute a system and guide on crafting powerful speeches and writing. It is also a template by which to judge effective rhetoric. The five canons were brought together and organized by the Roman orator, Cicero, in his treatise, *De Inventione*, written around 50 BC. In 95 AD (150 years later), the Roman rhetorician, Quintilian, explored the five canons in more depth in his landmark 12-volume textbook on rhetoric entitled *Institutio Oratoria*. This textbook, and consequently the five canons of rhetoric, went on to become the backbone of rhetorical education well into the medieval period. The five Canons of Rhetoric are expatiated here thus:

- i. **Inventio (invention):** The process of developing and refining your

arguments. At the invention level in the political communication speech writing, the speech writer invents a good political idea that he wants to communicate to the audience. However, before he could successfully carry out this activity, he must first find out in advance what the audience would want to hear, and why. The knowledge of the demographic and psychographic composition of the audience is very critical at this level as such knowledge would help in the choice of words to suit the specific audience for which the speech is meant. It is safe to note here that failure at this stage can negatively affect the rest of the stages.

- ii. **Dispositio (arrangement):** The process of arranging and organizing your arguments for maximum impact. At this stage, all the topics which were identified and collected at the invention stage are composed and refined. This is done in order to create a cohesive argument that would be able to convince members of the audience. It is at this stage that the structure of the speech is arranged. It is at this stage that the speech writer decides whether he will throw rhetorical questions at the members of his audience at certain points during the speech, or whether the salient points in the speech are to be repeated at the concluding part of the speech.
- iii. **Elocutio (style):** The process of determining how you present your arguments using figures of speech and other rhetorical techniques. The artistic and fun aspect of the speech is decided at this stage. Also, the style of delivering the speech is decided at this stage of preparation. For instance, questions like, is the speech going to bring in humour? Will it be purely an informational speech? What words are chosen and what decisions are going to be made in order to influence the audience? All these kinds of questions are answered at the elocution stage of speech preparation.
- iv. **Memoria (memory):** This entails the process of learning and memorizing your speech so you can deliver it without the use of notes. Memory-work not only consist of memorizing the words of a specific speech, but also storing up famous quotes, literary references, and other facts that could be used in impromptu speeches. It is at the

memoria stage that the proficiency of the speech presenter is put to test. Is the speaker able to remember the speech word for word? Is he able to use famous quotes during the delivery? Is he able to make references to facts and figures during the speech presentation? These and many other questions bordering on the integrity of the speaker are considered at this stage.

- v. **Actio (delivery):** This is the last stage of the five canons of rhetoric, and it is about the effective use of non-verbal communication cues such as gestures, facial expressions, pronunciation, tone of voice, and postures. The stage of delivery and the proficiency of the speaker would determine whether members of the audience would give the speech presenter a standing ovation at the end of the speech, or whether they will sleep through the speech.

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts a broad framework which depends on both **the Systemic Functional Linguistics Theory (SFL)** and **Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA)**. The two approaches are combined because CDA on its own has no tool for linguistic analysis. Also, CDA and SFL have some things in common in their analytical focus (Graham, 2003).

Systemic Functional Linguistics Theory

This study is anchored on Halliday's Systemic Functional Linguistics Theory. The rationale for anchoring the study on this theory is due to the fact that the theory facilitates the understanding of the function and use of language in a cultural and situational context. As a matter of fact, systemic functional linguistics is an approach which considers language as a system of meanings (Halliday, 1985). Bloor and Bloor (2004, p. 2) supporting this viewpoint state that when people use language, "their language acts produce or, more technically, *construct* meanings." According to Halliday (1985), language is structured to make three kinds of meanings simultaneously. These meanings, known as 'meta-functions', include:

- i. **The Interpersonal Meaning:** This entails the meaning about the interaction between the speaker and the hearer (Halliday & Hasan, 1989). In this particular type of meta-function, language is used to enable people to participate in communicative acts with other people,

to take on roles, and to express and understand feelings, attitudes and judgments (Bloor & Bloor, 2004).

ii. **The Experiential Meaning:** This entails the meaning about the representation of our experience in the real world. Here, language is used to organize, understand and express people's perception of the world and their own consciousness.

iii. **The Textual Meaning:** Language in this context is the one whose function is specifically that of creating text, of making the difference between language in the abstract and language in use (Halliday, 2002). This means that language is used to relate what is said (or written) to the rest of the text and to other linguistic events. As a matter of fact, these strands of meanings are all interwoven in the fabric of the discourse. This is why Halliday and Hasan (1989, p. 23) state that;

The meanings are woven together in a very dense fabric in such a way that, to understand them, we do not look separately at its different parts; rather, we look at the whole thing simultaneously from a number of different angles, each perspective contributing towards the total interpretation. That is the essential nature of a functional approach.

Moreover, Halliday (1985) observes that these meanings are related to the context of situation and lexico-grammar. Indeed, the context of situation includes three variables known as register variables. These are: the field of discourse (what is going on), the tenor of discourse (who are taking part) and the mode of discourse (role assigned to language).

The lexico-grammatical patterns realized by language are transitivity, mood and theme. Thus, for Halliday (1985), the field is expressed through the experiential meanings which are realized through the transitivity patterns. As for the mode, it is expressed through the textual meanings; these meanings are realized through the theme patterns.

Finally, the tenor is expressed through the interpersonal meanings; these textual meanings are realized through the mood and modality. This study is mainly concerned with aspects of experiential and interpersonal meanings. More specifically, it deals with transitivity and modality patterns.

- i. **Transitivity:** Transitivity is the realization of the experiential component of language in a speech. It refers to the way meanings are encoded in the clause and to the way different types of processes are represented in language (Simpson, 2004). Halliday (1985) argues that transitivity specifies the different types of processes that are organized in the language, and the structure by which they are expressed. For him, a process consists of three components which are: the process itself, the participants in the process, and the circumstances associated with the process. There are six main processes:
 - a. **Material process:** This involves the process of doing, particularly concrete or movement actions. There are two participants associated with this process; these are actor and goal.
 - b. **Mental process:** This entails the process of sensing, with two participants which are senser and phenomenon.
 - c. **Behavioral process:** This is the process embodying physiological actions, with behavior as the main participant.
 - d. **Verbal process:** This means the process of verbal actions. It includes three main participants: sayer or speaker, receiver and verbiage.
 - e. **Existential process:** This represents experience by positioning that 'there was/is something'. This process has only one participant, the existent.
 - f. **Relational process:** This includes attributive and identifying processes. In the attributive sub-type, an attribute is ascribed to some entity; either as a quality (intensive), as a circumstance or as a possession. It has two participants: the carrier and attribute. In the identifying mode, one entity is used to identify another; the relationship between them is one of token and value, of phenomenon and circumstance of time, or of owner and possession (Halliday, 1985).

The third component of clause as representation is circumstance. It is the name given to the elements which carry a semantic load, but are neither the process nor the participant. Circumstantial elements conflate with adjunct and the grammatical realization is adverb or prepositional phrase (Bloor & Bloor, 2004).

The Critical Discourse Analysis Theory

Critical discourse analysis (CDA) stems from a critical theory of language which sees the use of language as a form of social practice. All social practices are tied to specific historical contexts and are the means by which existing social relations are produced or contested and different interests are served. It is the questions pertaining to interests that relate discourse to relations of power. How is the text positioned or positioning? Whose interests are served by this positioning? Whose interests are negated? What are the consequences of this positioning? Where analysis seeks to understand how discourse is implicated in relations to power, it is called critical discourse analysis.

Fairclough's (2019) model for CDA consists of three interrelated processes of analysis which are tied to three interrelated dimensions of discourse. These three dimensions are:

1. The object of analysis (including verbal, visual or verbal and visual text);
2. The processes by which the object is produced and received (writing/speaking/designing and reading/listening/viewing) by human subjects;
3. The socio-historical conditions that govern this process.

According to Fairclough, each of these dimensions requires a different kind of analysis. These are:

1. Text analysis (description);
2. Processing analysis (interpretation);
3. Social analysis (explanation).

What is useful about this approach is that it enables the analyst to focus on the signifiers that make up the text, the specific linguistic selections, their juxtapositioning, their sequencing, and their layout. However, it also requires that the historical determination of these selections be recognized in order to understand that these choices are tied to the conditions of possibility. This is another way of saying that texts are instantiations of socially regulated discourses and that the process of production and reception are socially constrained. Why Fairclough's approach to CDA is so useful is that it provides multiple points of analytic entry. It does not matter which kind of analysis one begins with, as long as they are all included and are shown to be mutually

explanatory. It is in the interconnections that the analyst finds interesting patterns and disjunctions that need to be described, interpreted and explained.

Research Methodology

Design

This study adopts content analysis as described by Berelson (1952, P. 18). According to him, it is a “systematic and quantitative description of a manifest content of communication that can 'reveal the focus of attention' and also identify the intention of the communication”.

Materials

The data for this analysis comprises President Muhammadu Buhari's August 11, 2022 speech on the march 28, 2022 Abuja-Kaduna train attack. The researcher downloaded both the video and the transcript the speech. The video which was downloaded from <http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TzpgvXGuxyA>, was used to represent the real situation of the speech while using the transcript as the data. For the transcript, we relied on the publication of two nationally recognized newspapers, namely Vanguard and The Guardian.

Analysis Procedure

This involved several steps. As the first step, a comparison was made between the transcript and the original video of the president's speech to ensure that the transcript matched the spoken text. Taking into account the individual clauses with the presence or absence of rhetoric (that is, rhetorical canons and rhetorical proofs) under study, the speech was segmented into sentence units. In this connection, the presence or absence of rhetorical canons in the speech were identified by isolating canons and categorizing them into five – invention, arrangement, style, memory and delivery as explained in the conceptual review section of this study. The speech was also analyzed for compliance with the three variances of rhetorical proofs (logos, ethos and pathos). Sentences in the speech were carefully analyzed to ascertain its conformity to the canons and proofs of rhetoric as illustrated below.

Data Analysis and Discussion

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of INVENTION (*Inventio*)

Esuh (2006) states that invention involves the attempt by the speaker to investigate the subject matter of discourse. It embraces survey and forecasting of the subject and arguments suitable for any given rhetorical effort. It involves the idea of the status and modes of persuasion- logical, emotional and ethical, which are in themselves interrelated. Invention is the process of coming up with what you want to say to persuade members of the audience about your view. What are the key messages and points that will help you to convince your audience of your point of view? To achieve this, there is need for clarity of purpose and understanding of the subject and your audience. At this stage, you also need to choose your presentation style (and now days your medium) and decide how long your presentation should be.

Pudewa (2016) describes invention as the process of coming up with what to say. Its root is the Latin word *invenio*, meaning “to find or discover.” In order to write something, we must have something to write about. However, in the ancient rhetoric exercises known as the *progymnasmata*, the first task was not to “think of something to say” but to “retell a fable.” Imitation is vital to the learning of a skill. The relationship between the words shows a truth of creativity – to invent something, you have to need some stuff to begin with. One sad fact we all must face is that we cannot get something out of a mind that is not in there to begin with. We cannot use words we do not know. We cannot articulate concepts we do not understand. We cannot think thoughts we are incapable of thinking. This is why memory is the foundation of all.

The position of this paper is that the speech of President Muhammadu Buhari under review failed in this first task. The reason for this position is that the nation was in total lament and confusion, the youths were enraged, lives were lost in Lagos and across many states; therefore, words of healing, and advocacy for calmness and apologizing for the failure of government to institute police reforms and create jobs for the youths would have been a better way to start. The President's speech fell short of being Presidential, it failed to heal, unite, show empathy, and reconcile. This is why the speech was greeted with outrage all over the country. Many saw it as empty, a waste of time and insensitive.

At the invention phase in rhetorical communication, without some direction and guidance, brainstorming can often be fruitless and frustrating. Pondering on elements such as your audience, your evidence, the means of persuasion, timing and format of argument are important and these were lacking in the President's speech under review.

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of ARRANGEMENT (*dispositio*)

According to Esuh (2006), *dispositio* (disposition) covers the philosophy of arrangement and orderly presentation/planning of the idea to be discussed. It assesses the selection of the subject matter into structure, determining or emphasizing how each part contributes to the unity and purpose of the speech. Classically, a speech should have the proem, the narration and the epilogue, roughly equivalent to introduction, body and conclusion.

Walton (2000) defines arrangement as the process of deciding how to order the materials in a text. In writing, this is still part of the pre-writing stage. Speeches, like music, should be carefully arranged. Arrangement is the process of structuring your content. You need to put all the great things you thought of in the invention stage into a good order so that they work together and help persuade your audience. The President's claim that;

I have been informed that, at last count, there remained about 31 people in the hands of the kidnappers and our determination is to work towards returning these 31 people to their families. It is understandable that emotions typically run high, we have received several suggestions about the deployment of lethal military force in extracting those still being held in captivity. This option has, indeed, been considered and evaluated.

This part of the speech was at variance to the conformity with the Rhetoric Canons of Communication. From the speech, it was observed that he missed the opportunity to emotionally connect with the pains of families who lost their loved ones, those whom their relatives and or breadwinners were still in

captivity, knowing fully well that the incidence was, in itself, an indictment on the government and was capable of eroding confidence and patriotism. The speech portrayed the President as an insensitive leader who cared less about his subjects as he did not, in his entire speech, commiserate directly or indirectly with families that were grieving. If the President was sincere when he claimed that “the nation had joined them to endure a period of difficulty and emotional pains”, he never showed it in his speech or action, before, during or immediately after the attack. He missed an opportunity to show empathy and rise to the moment as 'Father of the nation'.

Soha (2010) supports this assertion when he states that because modern presidents display commitment and concern to a policy or issue through their public speeches – even if they are not typically successful leading public opinion – they lead by speaking about policy issues. Any variation in the level of attention through speeches, therefore indicates that presidents are altering their leadership or governing strategies to affect their political fortunes and assist in their goal achievement.

Modern arrangement of speeches usually has three stages: introduction, body and conclusion. The classical arrangement that Cicero would have used though had five stages: *introduction, state neutral facts, make your case, refute alternative positions, and conclude your presentation*. This arrangement can still be used if a speech writer wishes, though most people go with the three-stage approach. It is important to think about arrangement across all forms and mediums of communication and ensure that what is chosen is right for the audience and the chosen medium. According to Brett and McKay (2020), arrangement is simply the organization of a speech or text to ensure maximum persuasion.

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of STYLE (*Elocution/elocutio*)

Soha (2010, P. 19) states that “presidents themselves believe that ineffective communication contributes to a failure of governance. Both Presidents Clinton and Reagan, for instance, lamented that their inability to lead the public was failure to communicate policy initiatives clearly. As others have argued, moreover, it is through devoting commitment and concern to a policy that demonstrates presidential leadership.” To Esuh (2006, P. 9), *elocution*

(elocution) simply means "styles or the concept of expression in language, resulting from the choice of words or the arrangement of the composition. Style is usually classified as plain, moderate, elated or grand".

Walton (2010) notes that style is the process of coming up with the actual words that will be used in a text. In writing, this canon is first approached in the drafting stage and continues in the rewriting stage. Pudewa (2016) opines elocution basically means the way something is said. The vocabulary, sentence structure, and expressions used will affect the reader's perception of the ideas. Again, memory is critical because the power of expressive language will be a function of the great database of language in the brain. Style is the process of choosing language and constructing your presentation so as to create an emotional response. Eloquence and structuring can help a speech presenter to achieve this outcome. Also, the skillful use of emotive language and rhetorical devices such as analogy, allusion and alliteration can help the speech presenter to convince his audience members.

According to Brett and McKay (2020), when people write memos or give persuasive speeches, the focus is usually on what they are going to write or say. While it is important that you have something substantive to say, it is also important how you present your ideas. The canon of style will help you present your ideas and arguments so people will want to listen to you.

Interestingly, in President Buhari's speech under review, he lost the rhetoric canon of style when he said;

I have been informed that at last count, there remain about 31 people in the hands of the kidnappers, and our determination is to work towards returning these 31 people to their families .It is understandable that emotions typically run high, we have received several suggestions about the deployment of lethal military force in extracting those still being held in captivity. This option has indeed been considered and evaluated.

He, however, worsened the situation when he stated that “the condition to guarantee a successful outcome and minimize potential collateral damage could not be assured and, therefore, that course of action had to be reluctantly discarded.”

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of *Memory (Memoria)*

According to Esuh (2006), memory refers to the speaker's mastery of key elements of his material in sequential order associated with memorization. To this, Walton (2000) had earlier stated that memory is the process of committing a text to memory. Although this Canon is not as applicable to writing as it is to oratory, there are still occasions where writers must memorize their texts in order to make the delivery more effective.

Pudewa (2016) states that memory, of course, is where it all begins and ends. If, as was most often done in ancient times, one's rhetoric was spoken rather than written, it was critical that such speeches be well memorized and practiced for a powerful delivery. However, the function of memory as a component of rhetoric goes far beyond just memorizing a speech. The modern educationists, who condemn memorization as useless, boring, rote, tedious, and harmful to children, fail to notice that if we had not memorized anything, we would not know anything. Hence, the ancients called memory “the furnishing of the mind.”

Memory relates to remembering enough so that you can present fully and fluently, without notes. This was essential in the Roman era when the canons were written and orators needed to speak for hours at a time. While it is perhaps slightly less important now, it is still a very useful skill. Many great speakers visualize their presentations in advance, do “dress rehearsals”, explore their environments and understand multiple layers of their presentations (from full text to a few key bullet points).

The rhetorical canon of memory was the worst victim in the speech under review. Agreed President Buhari has never been a good orator, but nowhere from start to finish of his address did he show mastery of any key element of his speech. All through, he was glued to his script. Memorization became a victim of his inadequate rhetorical skill.

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of DELIVERY

Esuh (2006) states that delivery involves the skill of maximizing the vocal elements in relation to the bodily actions to achieve effective delivery. Walton (2000) defines delivery as the process of presenting a text to an audience. Like memory, delivery is less prominent in writing than in oratory. However, there are many occasions where writers must think of how best to deliver their texts. Delivery is the last of the five canons of rhetoric. It involves using all the tools available to you to effectively communicate. Emphasis, tone of voice, change of pace, pauses, volume, gesticulation, body language, positioning and props are all tools to help effectively deliver your arguments.

Soha (2010) states that speeches are a primary tool available to modern presidents to alter their current political situation and help them to govern. As such, presidents should anticipate when delivering more (or fewer) speeches.

It can be stated clearly here that the delivery of President Buhari's speech under review was generally poor. But his poor delivery, it must be noted, is also influenced by his mother tongue. Not only did the body language, gesture and mien failed to "connect", but nothing indicated the President was feeling remorseful about government's failure at providing security which is the primary duty of any government.

This assertion is supported by Brett and McKay (2020) who state that like the canon of style, the canon of delivery is concerned with how something is said and not just being forced to the script. While the canon of style focuses primarily on what sort of language you use, delivery focuses on the mechanics of how you impart your message. For ancient orators, delivery meant how a speaker used his body language and hand gestures and how he changed his tone of voice during his oration. Mastering the canon of delivery can help a speaker establish ethos with his audience.

The most disappointing aspect of the speech was the fact that all through the entire delivery process, never did he rise to the occasion by using his speech to give hope, restore faith and confidence and bring succour to the families.

The President, through his speech was supposed to inspire hope and calm frayed nerves. Unfortunately, this was not the case.

Analysis of President Buhari's Speech of August 11, 2022 Presented to the Families of the Abuja-Kaduna Train Attack Victims in Conformity with the Rhetoric Canon of Proofs

According to Esuh (2006), "rhetorical proofs or supports are of classical origin, modern rhetoric only builds on them. Aristotle had theorized that the models of persuasion depending on the effects they produce in listeners are of three kinds, consisting in the moral character of the speaker – ethos or ethical proof; or in the production of a certain disposition in the audience –pathos or pathetic proofs; or in the speech itself by means of real or apparent demonstration – logos or logical proofs.

Ethos is appealed based on the character of the speaker. An ethos-driven document relies on the reputation of the author. According to Esuh (2006), “ethical proof concerns the speaker's credibility and the extent to which he is held by his audience. Good character, good sense, and concern for the welfare of the audience are the three constituents of ethical appeal. Ethos deals with the credibility of the speaker. To put it differently, ethos hinges on the trust that the members of the audience have on the speaker. There are three kinds of ethos in speech delivery. These are i) Initial ethos which has to do with the level of credibility that members of the audience have about the speaker the before the speech; ii) Desired ethos which is based on the content and delivery pattern of the speech itself; and iii) Post ethos which is ethos perceived by the audience about the speaker (and the speech) after the message. The three major constituents of ethos are sagacity or good sense, good moral character and goodwill, which are generally referred to as the three Gs of persuasive communication.

Pathos is appealed based on emotion. Advertisements tend to be pathos-driven. According to Esuh (2006, P. 31);

Pathetic Proof is the simplest way of understanding the tenets of pathos. Without the audience, there is no speech. The speech situation is a third-dimensional transaction and the audience disposition is as valid as other

components of the speaker and the speech itself. It is inferred that the audience is the most important element in the speech situation and that if the speaker is to be effective, he must adjust himself and his ideas to suit the audience. Pathetic proof is also called emotional proof. It must be designed and used to put the audience in a frame of mind to react favorably and comfortably to the purpose of the speech situation. If by any means the audience is not put in a favorable frame to be moved, the speech will lose its potency.

Logos is appealed based on logic or reason. Documents distributed by companies or corporations are logos-driven. Scholarly documents are also often logos-driven. Esuh (2006) states that "logical proof refers to the basic elements of the speech itself which the speaker employs to alter the consciousness of his audience. The two main elements of logical proofs are:

- a. **Evidence:** This refers to inartistic proofs which are not created by the speaker, the raw materials used to establish an issue. It includes testimony of people, exhibits, witnesses, oaths, statistics, photographs/illustration, oral and video recording and other 'factual' matters capable of inducing agreement or belief.
- b. **Argument:** This refers to the artistic proof, which is the ability of the speaker to create line of argument out of existing evidence. Evidence without creativity may lack the potency to bite.

Buhari's speech in question lacked ethos needed under the circumstance. Ethos suffered tremendously in this speech. His viewers and listeners had many reasons not to trust whatever he was saying. The speech itself was made worse by lacking the desired ethos it ought to have come with. From start to finish, either deliberately or by error, the address made no single reference to the Lekki Toll Gate crisis. An opportunity to evoke emotional appeal that connects with sensitivity and empathy was lost. This explains why outrage, frustration, disappointment grew higher after the speech than before it.

A Presidential speech at this time would have centered on calming tempers, appealing for calmness and most significantly, apologizing. For instance, the following statements in the speech were not necessary:

Judging by the available reports to me and news that have begun emerging in the last few days, I will say they have heard this instruction and are responding appropriately..... In the past couple of days, you must have heard about the number of terrorists neutralized by the military, and number of hostages freed. These efforts will not stop, or reduce..... We must take the fight to the terrorists and demonstrate that there is no hiding place for them within the borders of our country. Each one of them will be hunted, and pursued and spoken to in the language that they understand.

The speech was so dry and lacking in human emotions. Therefore, not only was the speech lacking in logos, but the President failed to utilize the few data and facts he had and to deliver same in a manner that advanced his course and believability. His attempt to praise the efforts of security forces lacked the artistic proof capable of making any emotional impact on the victim's relatives.

Conclusion

Speech is a two-way face-to-face communication. In this case, speech is the result of the process of thinking by a person who poured in the activities of speaking to the general public by providing a sequence of exposure in form of systematic presentation of information with the purpose of listeners understanding and following the communicator's intentions. Thus, rhetoric can be regarded as the ability to process various means of language in certain situations and certain purposes in the activities of communicating.

The President's speech in the aftermath of the Abuja train attack, failed the test of leadership, of being presidential and of being sober. The lack of rhetorical canons and proofs in the speech further showed the president as a leader who has lost touch and got disconnected with the reality of life as it never inspired, consoled, comforted, gave neither hope nor solace, but dampened patriotism and pride in nationhood. Priority must, therefore, be made to ensure that the

rhetorical canons are strictly adhered to in future presidential speeches especially in moments of crisis as almost all crises communication management techniques are embedded in the rhetorical canons.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, it is hereby recommended that;

- i. Presidential speech writers should consider the importance of adopting the five rhetoric canons of *inventio*, *dispositio*, *elucutio*, *memoria* and delivery in future speech writing to aid delivery of speeches that will inspire, arouse and appeal to emotions.
- ii. Efforts should be made to tutor the President on the need to improve on his elocution while making future speeches.
- iii. Future speeches by the President should consider the sensitivity of issues at stake, the mood of the nation and evoke rhetorical skills that will appeal more to emotions and connect the President with the people, rather than make him look distant and disconnected from the people or from reality as the speech indicated.
- iv. The power of silence or pause in delivery should be adopted in future speeches by the President in a manner that allows body language and gestures to communicate his association with the feelings of the audience.
- v. Finally, efforts should be intensified to improve the President's ability to use the rhetorical skill of memory in future speeches. Such effort would help to reduce his over dependence on the script.

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